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Review Article

A Comprehensive Review Of Herbal And Synthetic Wound Healing Creams

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

The potential of medicinal plants and their extracts in stimulating wound healing is indicated by the abstracts and conclusions of several studies on herbal and commercially available wound healing creams. Combinations of various medicinal plant extracts have demonstrated good consistency, spreadability, and wound-healing capacity. Research has demonstrated how crucial natural sources are to creating the best possible wound care creams. Additionally, the efficient use of natural wound-healing materials has been aided by recent developments in skin delivery techniques. These results demonstrate the potential for safe and effective treatment options for a variety of wound types as well as the intriguing role of herbal creams in wound care.

Body of abstract:

This review gives the researcher a thorough overview of the classification of wounds as well as a detailed classification of creams, benefits and drawbacks of creams. It gives researchers the comprehensive general instructions needed to make the creams. Additionally, it provides a comparison of commercially available herbal and synthetic wound healing lotions. It gives the researcher the steps needed to assess the creams.

Conclusion:

This review provides you with detailed information about the Herbal and Synthetic creams.

INTRODUCTION

Creams are topical drugs that can be administered topically to the skin. "Viscous liquid or semi-solid emulsions of either the oil-in-water or water-in-oil type" are what are referred to as creams. The

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consistency of the mixture depends on the type of oil and water.[1] Creams are used for medicinal or cosmetic functions, as well as for cleaning, beautifying, and improving appearances.[2] Creams are considered pharmaceutical items since they are manufactured utilizing techniques developed in the pharmaceutical industry. Creams with and without medication are frequently used to treat dermatoses and other skin conditions. Allopathic, herbal, and ayurvedic creams can be used by people according to the needs of their specific skin conditions. They include one or more medication ingredients that were previously distributed out or diluted appropriately. Creams can be classified as w/o or o/w forms of emulsion based on phase. Semisolid compositions classified as oil-in-water or water-in-oil (cold cream, for example) have historically been called "cream." (As in, cream that vanishes). [3] The medication that is integrated may be natural, semi-natural, or synthetic. Plants are the main source of natural products, while they can also be made from animals and dirt. A vast variety of chemical compounds found in plants have medicinal significance. They are rich in secondary metabolites, and a single plant can have a wide range of physiologically significant active chemicals in it.[4] A class of drugs known as herbal medicines uses plant parts, including flowers, seeds, stems, leaves, roots, and other components, to treat, prevent, and improve health. Herbal preparations are mixtures of one or more herbs, or processed herbs through a variety of methods, including distillation, maceration, concentration, infusion, decoction, and purification. These mixtures provide specific nutritional, cosmetic, or

other advantages meant to alter the physiology or structure of human or animal bodies, or to detect, treat, ameliorate, or otherwise improve disorders in humans or animals. Approximately 70% of Indians consume herbal medicines these days for medical conditions. All that the herbal cream is is an oil and water emulsion. The herbal cream was made using these organic ingredients: papaya, tulsi, aloe vera, neem turmeric, etc. [5] Formulations such as skin protection, sunscreen, anti-acne, and anti-wrinkle, whether natural or synthetic, are available for a variety of skin conditions. Quality requirements need to be upheld during the formulation development process for cosmetics. Herbal products have no negative effects when compared to synthetic formulations because the herbs employed in cosmetic preparations contain a variety of qualities, such as anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antibacterial, and antioxidant activities.[6] Due its chemical affinity for propolis, ethanol is the first solvent that is advised for use in the many techniques used around the world to extract propolis extracts. Chloroform, water, methanol, and ethylic ether are just a few instances of solvents that may be indicated for the extraction of particular propolis compounds. [7] Gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, which are significant pathogens in nosocomial infections connected to catheters, implants, and prostheses, were tested for propolis' antibacterial activity.[8] Wax and other organic residues are eliminated during the ethanol extraction process, which is an additional benefit [9].

TYPES OF HERBAL CREAMS

Skin creams are divided into groups based on their functions, which include massage, foundation, cleansing, and special attributes like cooling or disappearing creams. the emulsion types. Four different kinds of creams,

- COLD CREAM
- VANISHING CREAM
- CLEANSING CREAM
- MOISTURISING CREAM

COLD CREAM:

The water in oil emulsion is referred to as cold cream. Compared to other semi-solid dosage forms or formulations that are cold cream delivers an extended contact time at the application site. They make the skin appear more elegant and less oily. The oil phase nourishes the skin considerable emollience. The objective of the cold cream is to cool the body and refill moisture to dry skin through eliminating debris from the pores. It is effortless to remove away and is easily dissolved in water. They fail to protect the skin in any other manner. It disintegrates in natural pores at body temperature.[12]

VANISHING CREAM:

They are blends of oil painting with water. They spread as a thin, undetectable oil painting-like

layer by layer over the outermost layer of the skin when applied to the face. They have become known as vanishing creams because a result. It is created by utilizing an alkali that includes potassium hydroxide, sodium hydroxide, borax, etc. for emulsifying stearic acid and water. One of the key components in evaporating cream the fact that gives the cream their pearly white colour is stearic acid. evaporating cream produces enhanced activity along with fewer negative consequences when it is formulated with a botanical extract of neem and turmeric.[13]

MOISTURISING CREAM:

The water in oil emulsion is recognized as moisturizing cream. Contrasting moisturizing cream to other semisolid dosage forms or formulations that are the previous type offers prolonged contact time at the application site. They make the skin appear delicate and less oily. The oil phase nourishes skin various emolliences. In spite of enabling contaminants to be eliminated through pores and refreshing the body, hydrating lotions also serve the purpose of supplementing moisture to dry skin. When applied to the skin, they cause not any discomfort. The water phase preserves the skin even further. At body

temperature, it evaporates. It permeates the skin from the epidermis by natural pores.[14]

CLEANSING CREAM:

These creams are used for detoxifying the body and restore one's personal hygiene and splendour, as well as both which are necessary for applying makeup. Makeup, dirt, and oil can be eliminated mainly from the face and neck using cleansing creams or lotions.[15]

WOUND:

A wound is a disruption in the skin's continuity. "Disruption of normal anatomic structures and function" is the explanation provided for it. Wounds continued to be an emotive clinical problem in everyday life, having both early and late repercussions routinely resulting in morbidity and mortality.[16] Figure:1

Figure:1Types of wounds

WOUND HEALING HERBAL CREAMS

Physical injuries that cause the skin to split or open up are called wounds. For the skin's compromised functional state and damaged anatomical continuity to be restored, wound healing must be done properly. Nowadays, the entire world including affluent nations recognizes the value of traditional medicine and promotes research on herbal or ethnomedical remedies since they are safer and less harmful.[17]

ALOE VERA

They perform effectively on dry and irritated skin because they give the skin-deep nourishment and natural moisture. Aloe vera creams feature a light-textured, fast-absorbing composition. The plant's gel-like components are well known for curing a range of mild skin conditions. They function as a skin-care anti-aging component. Aloe vera has the potential to reduce inflammation and itching associated with skin disorders such as psoriasis. They might also aid in the relief of eczema-related dry, itchy skin. Aloe vera's anti-inflammatory properties could aid in the treatment of inflammatory acne. Six antiseptic compounds found in aloe vera have the ability to suppress bacteria, viruses, and fungi. When used topically, aloe vera dramatically boosts collagen synthesis by activating and multiplying fibroblasts, which promotes wound healing.[1]

CEDRUS DEODARA

The creams have analgesic and anti-inflammatory ingredients that help lessen pain, swelling, and inflammation, they are beneficial in treating skin conditions that cause discomfort and itching. The creams' antibacterial and antifungal properties can help cure skin conditions like boils, acne, warts, and other infections as well as fungal infections. The lotions' antioxidants help protect the skin from free radical damage, which can worsen signs of aging such as wrinkles and age spots. It has been found that the creams aid in the accelerated healing of burns and other wounds by promoting the

creation of collagen, neovascularization, and epithelium.[18]

CENTELLA ASIATICA

Centella asiatica is beneficial in hydrating the skin and minimizing trans epidermal water loss. Triterpenoid saponins, flavonoids, and phenolic acids are among the bioactive substances found in Centella asiatica extract that support skin hydration. Many pharmacological actions, including anti-inflammatory ones, are displayed by substances derived from Centella asiatica. Acne, warts, and boils are just a few of the skin ailments and illnesses that the creams' antimicrobial qualities might help heal. There are antibacterial and antifungal properties reported in Centella asiatica. They can support the healing of wounds and aid in repairing skin damage.[19]

CHAMOMILLA RECUTITA

Chamomile creams include potent anti-inflammatory properties due to the presence of substances like chamazulene and alpha-bisabolol. Chamomile creams are advantageous for sensitive or inflammatory skin disorders since they aid in the calming and soothing of irritated skin. Creams containing chamomile can relieve redness, itching, and pain associated with skin disorders like dermatitis and eczema. Flavonoids, among other antioxidants found in chamomile, aid in the fight against free radicals, which can harm skin and hasten the aging process. Creams containing chamomile offer gentle antibacterial qualities that promote the skin's natural healing process, helping small cuts, wounds, and abrasions heal. Because of its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.[20]

CALENDULA OFFICIALISE

Creams containing calendula have anti-inflammatory qualities that help calm sensitive, inflamed skin. Creams containing calendula oil may be useful in the treatment of mild burns, dermatitis, and eczema. The antibacterial and wound-healing effects of flavonoids and

terpenoids are present in the creams. They may facilitate the healing of small lacerations, scratches, and abrasions. Creams containing calendula may boost skin moisture by reducing trans epidermal water loss and improving skin hydration. It has been discovered that they work well for scars, acne, and pimples. Calendula's antibacterial qualities could aid in the healing of skin ailments. Creams containing calendula can aid in preserving fair, wrinkle-free, and smooth skin.[10]

CHROMOLAENA ODORATA

The creams' Chromolaena odorata extracts have been shown to successfully treat and prevent common skin issues like wrinkles, lines, sagging, hyperpigmentation, and age spots that are brought on by chronoageing or photoaging. Strong antioxidants found in plant extracts shield fibroblasts and keratinocytes in vitro, which may promote improved wound healing.

Extracts from Chromolaena odorata have demonstrated antibacterial qualities that may help with the healing of wounds and the treatment of skin infections.[21]

AZADIRACHTA INDICA

Azadirachta indica, commonly known as Neem, has been traditionally used for its medicinal properties. Many skin conditions such as ulcers, boils, eczema, scabies, burning, and irregular pigmentation can be treated with it. It may address problems with skin pigmentation and promote general skin health. There are no known adverse effects of azadirachta indica cream in the medical literature. It is thought to be safe to use while nursing or pregnant.[22]

CURCUMA LONGA

Creams can be made from Curcuma longa extracts that are high in curcumin. These creams may be used to treat dry skin, psoriasis, eczema, hyperpigmentation, dark spots, and acne. Because

turmeric has germicidal and antioxidant qualities, it can help delay the aging process of the skin. They might also guard against skin damage and aid in wound healing. The primary ingredients that contribute to the advantages for skin include turmerones, desmethoxycurcumin, and curcumin. Turmeric creams can be made with urea, cyclodextrin, titanium dioxide, and derivatives of cellulose and formed as oil-in-water emulsions. To guarantee the stability and skin penetration of the active ingredients, proper formulation is crucial.[23]

ECHINACEA

Creams containing echinacea are very helpful for treating persistent skin illnesses like acne and infected eczema. They can support the maintenance of skin condition and relieve irritated, spot-prone skin. Freshly harvested, organically grown Echinacea purpurea herb and root extracts are used to make the lotions. Instead of using dried herbs, they are created with fresh herb tinctures. Echinacea creams are appropriate for daily skin care regimens since they work well under makeup and can be used as a daily face moisturizer. [9]

GINKGO BILOBA

Strong antioxidants like terpenoids and flavonoids found in them aid in the reduction of inflammation and the fight against free radicals. This may enhance the general health and look of the skin. Creams that contain ginkgo biloba extract may assist to brighten skin and encourage a more youthful appearance. The skin may feel tighter and more revitalized as a result. Daily use of the creams has been shown to improve skin texture and contour and lessen the appearance of wrinkles. They have anti-aging benefits that are visible to the eye. Topical application of ginkgo biloba creams is generally safe and well-tolerated.[24] wound healing herbal creams are shown in tabel:[1]

Table:1 wound healing herbs and therapeutic effects

Main Ingredients	Therapeutic Effects	Reference
Aloe Vera	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial activity, Wounds.	[1]
Cedrus deodara	anti-inflammatory, wound-healing, antibacterial, cure infected wounds.	[18]
Centella asiatica	Treatment of skin diseases, wounds, and leprosy	[19]
Chamomilla recutita	antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-healing medication	[20]
Calendula officinalis (marigold)	Anti-inflammatory, antibacterial activities; increase fibroblast migration	[10]
Chromolaena odorata	treatment of soft tissue and burn wounds, wound healing	[21]
Azadirachta indica	antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory activities, Improve wound healing	[22]
Curcuma longa	Antiseptic, antimicrobial, antiviral, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory, wound healing	[23]
Echinacea	Wound healing and wound contraction	[9]
Ginko biloba	improved mental clarity, antioxidant, membrane stabilizing, pro-healing, and increased blood fluidity	[24]

WOUND HEALING SYNTHETIC CREAMS

Antibiotics in biotechnology and medicine seem to be well-suited for formulations with distinct chemical compositions. Different antibiotic-loaded hydrogels have been created in the past few decades as antibacterial coatings and the treatment of diabetic wounds, burns, and superficial injuries. By releasing antibiotics at the location of the wound, these materials help to speed up the healing process and prevent infection. Antibiotics used locally dramatically lessen the undesirable side effects that are frequently linked to systemic usage.[25]

SOFRAMYCIN

Framycetin, an antibiotic included in soframycin creams, acts by preventing bacterial development on the skin. These creams work well for small burns, wounds, and infections. They can also be used to treat external ear infections, open wounds infected with germs, and bacterial infections of the skin, hair, and nails. Creams containing soframycin are useful for treating bacterial skin

diseases, such as impetigo, boils, and infected hair follicles.[26]

NEOSPRIN

Neosporin creams include three active ingredients: polymyxin B, bacitracin, and neomycin. These lotions are used to treat and prevent superficial bacterial skin infections from occurring on unintentional cuts, scratches, minor burns, wounds, and wound sutures. They are effective in treating bacterial skin infections, such as boils, hair follicle infections, and impetigo. Neosporin creams work by stopping the growth of germs that cause skin infections, which promotes the healing of minor cuts and wounds.[1]

SILVER NITRATE

Silver nitrate creams contain silver nitrate, an antiseptic and antibacterial agent. It works by discharging silver ions into the skin, which either eradicate or halt the development of contagious microorganisms. Minor skin wounds are treated with creams containing silver nitrate to stop the bleeding, cauterize the surrounding affected tissues, and stop infections.

They can also be used to get rid of skin tags or warts.[1]

CETRIMIDE

Creams containing cetrimide work efficiently to both prevent and treat infections in small burns, scratches, abrasions, and wounds. They aid in keeping the impacted area tidy. This type of inflammation of the skin is identified as seborrheic dermatitis, and it can be treated with these treatments. Microorganisms are killed and their proliferation is inhibited by the antibacterial, antifungal, and antiseptic characteristics of cetrimide.[1]

BETADINE

Betadine creams contain povidone-iodine, a strong component found in betidine creams, is effective in combating dangerous bacteria, viruses, and fungus. These lotions are applied to mild burns, scratches, scrapes, and grazes. Through the creation of a barrier that keeps bacteria at bay, they aid in the prevention of infection and the promotion of recovery. Cold sores, canker sores, and oral pain are among the skin and mucous membrane illnesses that beddedine creams can residence.[26]

SILVER SULPHADIAZINE

Silver sulfadiazine, an antibiotic that inhibits bacterial growth on the skin, is an ingredient in silver sulfadiazine creams. These lotions are applied to minor burns, scrapes, and wounds to cure and prevent infections. They lessen inflammation and encourage healing by preventing the growth of bacteria.[1]

CIPROFLOXACIN

Ciprofloxacin is the active component in ciprofloxacin creams. These creams are used to

treat a range of conditions, such as bacterial infections, including skin infections, fluid buildup in the retina, and fungal infections of the skin folds and armpit. Ciprofloxacin-containing creams prevent bacteria from proliferating by inhibiting DNA synthesis.[27]

MINOCYCLINE

The active ingredient in minocycline creams is minocycline. These creams are used to treat rosacea, acne, and other skin conditions like impetigo, cellulitis, and folliculitis. Minocycline-containing creams work by reducing inflammation, promoting healing, and stopping the growth of bacteria that cause infections.[28]

COTRIMOXAZOLE

Cotrimoxazole creams involve a combination of the antimicrobial agent and sulfamethoxazole as the effective ingredients. These products are used to treatment fungal infections, breakouts; rosacea, and microbial infections, include skin infections. Carboxazole-containing creams work by reducing inflammation, hastening the healing process, and inhibiting the growth of bacteria and fungi that cause infections.[29]

CLINDAMYCIN

Clindamycin is the active ingredient of clindamycin creams, which are used to treat bacterial infections, fungal infections, acne, rosacea, and skin infections. Clindamycin creams function by decreasing inflammation and encouraging healing by preventing the growth of bacteria and fungus that cause infections.[30] wound healing synthetic creams are shown in tabel:[2]

Table:2 wound healing synthetic and therapeutic effects

MAIN INGREDIENTS	THERAPEUTIC EFFECTS	REFERENCE
Soframycin	Healing wounds, cuts, burns, inflammation.	[26]
Neosprin	Burns infections, minor cuts, and wounds.	[1]
Silver Nitrate	Wounds, anti-infective agent, antiseptic.	[1]
Cetrimide	Antiseptic, Healing wounds ,minor burns, scalds.	[1]
Betadine	Antiseptic, minor cuts, abrasions, burns,	[26]

Silver Sulphadiazine	treat wound, burns wounds,	[1]
Ciprofloxacin	antibiotics, wound healing	[27]
Minocycline	Antimicrobial, Acne vulgaris	[28]
Cotrimoxazole	Soft tissue, infections, Cellulitis, and abscess	[29]
Clindamycin	Antibiotic, antimicrobial, Acne vulgaris.	[30]

GENERAL PREPARATION FOR CREAM

Creams are semisolid dosage forms that consist of one or more active ingredients dispersed in a suitable base. There are different methods for preparing creams, depending on the type and composition of the base and the active ingredients. [31] Some of the common methods as shown in following steps:

METHODS AND FORMULATION OF CREAMS

Cream formulations were developed from a o/w or w/o emulsion cream. The final developed formulations were used for the preparation of all cream formulations developed and tested are shows below,[32]

Formulation of o/w emulsion creams:

The formulation of oil in water emulsion cream are shown in following steps:

- The Preservatives And Water-Soluble Chemicals Are Taken And Melted At 75°C In A Different Beaker
- The Emulsifier And Oil-Soluble Ingredients Are Removed From One Beaker And Melted In A Water Bath
- The Water Phase Was Added To The Oil Phase Gradually While It Heated In A Mortar And Pestle
- The Mixture Was Centrifuged Until A Clicking Sound Was Produced
- Finally, Aromatic Agent And Preservatives Are Added When The Temperature Drops.

Formulation Of W/O Emulsion Creams:

- The Formulation Of Water In Oil Emulsion Cream Are Shown In Following Steps

- In An Individual Beaker, The Emulsifier And The Oil-Soluble Ingredients Are Melted At 75°C.
- In Addition, Ingredients That Dissolve In Water Are Removed And Melted In A Second Beaker At 75°C.
- In A Mortar And Pestle, The Water Phase Is Set Aside During Melting, And The Oil Phase Is Gradually Added And Stirred Until A Clicking Sound Is Produced.
- Finally, Aromatic Agent And Preservatives Are Added When The Temperature Drops.

EVALUATION PERAMETERS

Cream products were characterized by Physical appearance, pH measurement, Spreadability, Viscosity, Determination of Microbial growth they are shows below;

Physical appearance:

Colour, Odor, and phase separation were among the organoleptic characteristics that were observed.[33]

pH measurement:

Standard buffer solution was applied for pH meter calibration. A digital pH meter was utilized to measure the pH of 0.5 grams of cream that was previously weighed and dissolved in 50 millilitres of purified water.[34]

Spreadability:

The sample was placed between two slides to test the spreadability of the developed cream, and it was eventually compacted to a consistent thickness using a specific weight for a predetermined amount of time. Spreadability was defined as the duration of time needed to divide the two slides into detached portions.

Spreadability was determined using the subsequent formula:

Formula:

$$S=(M \times L) / T$$

Whereas

S = Spread ability

M= Weight tide uphill on the slide

L= Glass slide Length

T = Time needed to divide the slides.[35]

Viscosity:

A Brooke field viscometer was used to determine the viscosity of the cream at 25 °C and 2.5 rpm spindle number 63.[36]

Determination of Microbial growth:

- In-vitro Anti- Bacterial studies:
- In-vitro Antifungal studies:

In-vitro Anti- Bacterial studies:

Preparation of Nutrient media:

In 1 litter of distilled water, suspend 28 grams of nutritional agar powder. Dissolve to completely dissolve them. Sterilize in an autoclave set at 121°C for 15 minutes. While the medium has solidified, pour the liquid into the petridish. In order to avoid any contamination, prepare the agar in a clean environment.[37]

Determination of zone of inhibition:

The hole punch device was used to create holes in every plate. One milligram of the prepared cream was added to the petri plates with the microorganisms *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Similar to that, two serving dishes were added with the marketed goods. These plates were kept in an incubator for an extended period of 24 to 48 hours. Plates were analyzed for the zone of inhibition the next day.[37]

In-vitro Antifungal studies:

Preparation of Sabouraud dextrose Agar Plates:
Soak 65.0 grams in 1000 milliliters of purified water. To completely dissolve the medium, increase the temperature to a boil. For fifteen minutes, autoclave at 15 pounds of pressure (121°C). Increase temperature to 45–50°C. After completely mixing, transfer to sterile test tubes or Petri dishes. Until defects show up on them, store

prepared SDA plates or tubes between 2 and 8°C. [38]

Determination of zone of inhibition:

Add 1g of Formulated Creams to the Prepared Sabouraud dextrose Agar Plates. Inoculate the same surface with *Candida albicans*, let it grow for six days, then use a zone reader to determine and store the values of its zone of inhibition.[38]

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Formulation of w/o emulsion creams:

The formulation of water in oil emulsion cream are shown in following steps

- In An Individual Beaker, The Emulsifier And The Oil-Soluble Ingredients Are Melted At 75°C.
- In Addition, Ingredients That Dissolve In Water Are Removed And Melted In A Second Beaker At 75°C.
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Spreadability:

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General preparation for cream

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- The emulsifier and oil-soluble ingredients are removed from one beaker and melted in a water bath

- The water phase was added to the oil phase gradually while it heated in a mortar and pestle
- The mixture was centrifuged until a clicking sound was produced
- Finally, aromatic agent and preservatives are added when the temperature drops.

Formulation of w/o emulsion creams:

The formulation of water in oil emulsion cream are shown in following steps

- In an individual beaker, the emulsifier and the oil-soluble ingredients are melted at 75°C.
- In addition, ingredients that dissolve in water are removed and melted in a second beaker at 75°C.
- In a mortar and pestle, the water phase is set aside during melting, and the oil phase is

gradually added and stirred until a clicking sound is produced.

- Finally, aromatic agent and preservatives are added when the temperature drops.

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pH measurement:

Standard buffer solution was applied for pH meter calibration. A digital pH meter was utilized to measure the pH of 0.5 grams of cream that was previously weighed and dissolved in 50 millilitres of purified water.[34]

Spreadability:

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- In-vitro Anti- Bacterial studies:

- In-vitro Antifungal studies:

In-vitro Anti- Bacterial studies:

Preparation of Nutrient media:

In 1 liter of distilled water, suspend 28 grams of nutritional agar powder. Dissolve to completely dissolve them. Sterilize in an autoclave set at 121°C for 15 minutes. While the medium has solidified, pour the liquid into the petridish. In order to avoid any contamination, prepare the agar in a clean environment.[37]

Determination of zone of inhibition:

The hole punch device was used to create holes in every plate. One milligram of the prepared cream was added to the petri plates with the microorganisms *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Similar to that, two serving dishes were added with the marketed goods. These plates were kept in an incubator for an extended period of 24 to 48 hours. Plates were analyzed for the zone of inhibition the next day.[37]

In-vitro Antifungal studies:

Preparation of Sabouraud dextrose Agar Plates:

Soak 65.0 grams in 1000 milliliters of purified water. To completely dissolve the medium, increase the temperature to a boil. For fifteen minutes, autoclave at 15 pounds of pressure (121°C). Increase temperature to 45–50°C. After completely mixing, transfer to sterile test tubes or Petri dishes. Until defects show up on them, store prepared SDA plates or tubes between 2 and 8°C. [38]

Determination of zone of inhibition:

Add 1g of Formulated Creams to the Prepared Sabouraud dextrose Agar Plates. Inoculate the same surface with *Candida albicans*, let it grow for six days, then use a zone reader to determine and store the values of its zone of inhibition.[38]

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CONCLUSION

A number of studies that show the potential of medicinal plants and their extracts in improving wound healing have backed the use of herbal and commercial wound healing lotions. Combinations of extracts from many medicinal plants, such as *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Curcuma longa*, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Aloe vera*, have demonstrated good consistency, spreadability, and wound-healing capability. Application of natural wound-healing agents has also been made more effective by recent developments in skin delivery techniques. These results demonstrate the potential for safe and effective treatment options for a variety of wound types as well as the intriguing role of herbal creams in wound care.

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Aloe Vera

Centella asiatica

Cedrus deodara

Chamomilla recutita

Calendula officinalis

Azadirachta indica

Chromolaena

Curcuma longa

Echinacea

Ginkgo biloba

Soframycin

Silver Nitrate

Neosprin|

Betadine

Cetrimide

Ciprofloxacin

Silver Sulphadiazine

Minocycline

Cotrimoxazole

Clindamycin